

Hyperglycemia and Pancreatic Damage in Sucrose-Immersion-Induced Zebrafish

Alfiyah Salsabil¹

¹Faculty of Medicine, University of Islam Malang (UNISMA), Malang, Indonesia,

²Department of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine, Islamic University of Malang (UNISMA), Malang, Indonesia.

*Corresponding author: dinirisdamayanti@unisma.ac.id

Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease characterized by hyperglycemia and structural changes in the Langerhans islets and a decrease in the number of pancreatic beta cells [2]. Zebrafish is one of the animals that can be used as a model of hyperglycemia. The study aims to prove the effect of sucrose immersion on blood glucose levels and changes in Langerhans islet structure in zebrafish.

Laboratory research, and using posttest group control only research design. The research sample was 30 adult male zebrafish. The research groups consisted of Normal (N), G1 (1% sucrose immersion), G2 (2% sucrose immersion), and G3 (4% sucrose immersion). Sucrose induction is a modification of previous researchers [1],[4]. Sucrose induction was carried out for 28 days. The process of changing the bath water was carried out every 2 days. Zebrafish care followed laboratory procedures. At the end of the study, zebrafish were fed for 10 hours. The sacrifice process was carried out by placing the zebrafish in ice water for 10 minutes. After the fish was unconscious, the tail was cut to check fasting blood glucose levels using glucotest. Next, the pancreas organ was taken. Pancreatic organs were made in the form of prepartate histology with HE staining. Langerhans islet damage data were calculated manually, the number of cells experiencing pycnosis, karyorrhexis, karyolysis, vacuolization and diameter of the Langerhans islet then converted into a degree of damage [3]. Blood glucose data and islet Langerhans damage were analyzed using oneway ANOVA with a significance of $p < 0.05$.

The highest glucose level was achieved at G3 (188.67 ± 15.97 mg/dL) different from N (84.17 ± 5.71 mg/dL), G1 (131.67 ± 3.78 mg/dL) and G2 (137.83 ± 4.71 mg/dL) ($p < 0.05$). The level of Langerhans islet damage was highest in G3 (81.8%) compared to N (3.8%), G1 (33.8%) and G2 (62.65%) $p < 0.05$. The area of islets of Langerhans was smaller in G3 (7126.67 ± 1482.9) compared to N, G1 and G2 $p < 0.05$ and the diameter of Langerhans islet was smaller in G3 (69.698 ± 8.47 µm) compared to N, G1 and G2 $p < 0.05$.

Keywords: Sucrose, zebrafish, blood glucose and islet Langerhans

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease characterized by hyperglycemia or high glucose in the blood as a result of abnormalities in the secretion of the hormone insulin [1]. Diabetes mellitus is one of the degenerative diseases whose prevalence is increasing. In 2019, the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) organization estimated the number of people with diabetes in the world to be at least 463 million people in the population aged 20-79 years. As the population ages, the prevalence of diabetes is expected to increase to 111.2 million people aged 65-79 years. This figure will further increase to 578 million in 2030 and 700 million in 2045 [2]. In ideal conditions, diabetes management includes lifestyle changes, especially a healthy diet and increased physical activity. However, in reality, the prevalence of type 2 DM continues to increase, especially in developing countries, largely due to unhealthy dietary changes and modern lifestyles [3]. One important aspect in the pathogenesis of type 2 DM is the excessive consumption of sugar, especially sucrose, which is often present in packaged foods and beverages [4].

Hyperglycemia is a medical condition in which blood glucose levels exceed normal limits with a concentration of blood sugar during ≥ 200 mg/dl or fasting blood sugar ≥ 126 mg/dl [5]. Hyperglycemia is the initial trigger for insulin resistance, a condition in which the body's cells are unable to respond optimally to insulin [6]. Chronic hyperglycemia results in glucotoxicity in pancreatic islets of Langerhans β cells. This glucotoxicity results in dysfunction and changes in β -cell mass, which ultimately leads to decreased insulin secretion by β -cells and also reduced insulin receptor sensitivity. Abnormalities

in the mechanism of insulin secretion that occur will cause a decrease in glucose intake into cells and an increase in blood sugar levels, resulting in further hyperglycemia [7]. The imbalance between glucose transport into cells and insulin production by the pancreas causes Diabetes Mellitus (DM) [8].

Significant changes in the histological structure of pancreatic islets of Langerhans are one of the typical pathological features often found in patients and animal models of diabetes mellitus. One of the more popular animal models used in research is zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) has several advantages as an animal model, namely the zebrafish genome is similar to the human genome with respect to the number of chromosomes (25 and 23 pairs, respectively) and protein-coding genes. Humans and zebrafish share 70% of the same genes and 84% of human genes known to be associated with human diseases are also found in zebrafish [9]. In addition, zebrafish also have cardiovascular, nervous and digestive systems similar to mammals. This vertebrate zebrafish has a wide range of organs and cell types similar to mammals such as humans [5].

Previous research conducted by Ranjan and Sharma in 2018 stated that immersion with a maximum concentration of 4% sucrose can be used to induce hyperglycemia in zebrafish. Zebrafish regulate their internal water and salt concentrations through the process of hyperosmotic osmoregulation. This mechanism involves the continuous absorption of water, which can also include the absorption of other molecules from their environment such as glucose [8]. This study aims to see the pattern of hyperglycemia in zebrafish as a test model due to 1%, 2% and 4% sucrose immersion on the increase in blood sugar levels of pancreatic organ histology.

Materials and Methods

Time and Place of Research

This study is an *in vivo* laboratory study on zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) to determine the effect of 1%, 2% and 4% sugar administration for 28 days on the histopathological picture of Langerhans islets. This research was conducted from August to December 2023 at the Faculty of Fisheries and Marine Science (FPIK), Universitas Brawijaya, Malang. This research has been approved by the Islamic University of Malang Health Research Ethics Commission with certificate number No.077/LE.003/X/03/2023.

Research Samples

The samples in this study were zebra fish (*Danio rerio*) measuring 3-5 cm in the adult phase which were divided into 4 groups where 1 group with 1% exposure, 1 group with 2% exposure, 1 group with 4% exposure and 1 group without exposure.

Determination of the sample size in this study is based on calculations with the 1991 Federer formula obtained the results of 6 samples. In this study each group consisted of 30 fish to be placed in 5 different ponds. Each group contained 6 fish which were kept in 5 aquariums containing 2 L of water.

Research Design

One hundred and twenty adult male zebrafish were randomly divided into 4 groups: one control or normal group (N) and three treatment groups (G1, G2, G3). The control group did not receive any treatment while the treatment group will be induced by dissolving sucrose in the aquarium to make the fish experience hyperglycemia conditions according to research conducted by Ranjan and Sharma in 2018. Immersion using sucrose is varied in three different doses (G1: 1% sucrose immersion, G2: 2% sucrose immersion, G3: 4% sucrose immersion) to determine the difference in the effect of hyperglycemia caused by each dose on blood sugar levels and histopathological images of zebrafish Langerhans islets.

Data Analytics

Data will be presented as mean \pm SD. Differences between the mean blood sugar levels, damage, area and diameter of the islets of Langerhans will be analyzed using the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test if the results show significantly or significantly different then Duncan's further test is carried out to determine which treatment gives a significantly different response. A value of $p < 0.05$ indicates statistically significant results.

Results and Data Analysis

Blood sugar and histopathological examination of zebrafish pancreatic tissue was carried out after immersion using sucrose according to the treatment dose in experimental animals for 28 days. The analysis will be carried out in the form of average blood sugar levels of zebrafish, average damage to

islets of Langerhans, average area of islets of Langerhans and average diameter of islets of Langerhans obtained from histopathological examination of pancreatic tissue.

Blood Sugar Levels

Examination of blood sugar levels after immersion in sucrose solution with a concentration of 1%, 2% and 4% for 28 days using the GlucoDr tool found the highest blood sugar levels in group G3 followed by G2 and G1. The lowest blood sugar levels were found in the control group (N) when compared to G1, G2 and G3 ($p < 0.05$). The results of the calculation of the average blood sugar levels of zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) after immersion in sucrose solution with a concentration of 1%, 2% and 4% for 28 days using the GlucoDr tool can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean blood glucose level of Zebrafish

Groups	Mean \pm SD	p
N	84.17 \pm 5.71 ^a	0,00
G1	131.67 \pm 3.78 ^b	
G2	137.83 \pm 4.71 ^b	
G3	188.67 \pm 15.97 ^c	

Description: Table 1 is the mean blood glucose level of zebrafish in control group (N) and treatment groups 1% (G1), 2% (G2) and 3% (G3).

Different notations indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) with Duncan's post-hoc test.

Langerhans Island Damage

From the measurement of Langerhans islet damage, the highest level of Langerhans islet damage was found in G3 compared to group N ($p < 0.05$). The level of damage decreased gradually in G2, G1 and N. The level of damage to the islets of Langerhans is significantly different in each treatment group can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Mean Langerhans Island Damage

Groups	Mean \pm SD				Total Damages (%)	Description
	Pyknotic	Karyorrhexis	Karyolysis	Vacuolization		
N	0.3 \pm 0.5 ^a	1.0 \pm 1.1 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^a	0.0 \pm 0.0 ^a	3,8%	Normal
G1	14.0 \pm 1.7 ^b	14.7 \pm 2.1 ^b	12.0 \pm 1.9 ^b	9.0 \pm 2.4 ^b	33,8%	Mild
G2	26.3 \pm 1.5 ^c	23.7 \pm 1.5 ^c	23.3 \pm 3.7 ^c	22.3 \pm 1.5 ^c	62,65%	Moderate
G3	35.8 \pm 2.0 ^d	27.7 \pm 1.5 ^d	36.5 \pm 3.5 ^d	26.3 \pm 1.5 ^d	81,8%	Severe

Description: Different notations indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) with Duncan's post-hoc test.

Figure 1. Histopathology of zebrafish pancreas (*Danio rerio*) magnification 400X, HE staining
Description: A: Control group (N), B: 1% concentration group (G1), C: 2% concentration group (G2), D: 4% concentration group (G3), yellow arrow: pyknotic, blue arrow: karyorrhexis, green arrow: karyolysis, black arrow: vacuolization.

Diameter of Langerhans Island

The diameter of the islets of Langerhans in group N was larger when compared to treatment groups G1, G2 and G3. The smallest Langerhans islet diameter was obtained in group G3. The higher the dose of sucrose given, the smaller the diameter of the islets of Langerhans ($p < 0.05$) can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Mean Langerhans Island Diameter

Groups	Mean (μm) \pm SD	p
N	139.11 \pm 28.19 ^a	0,00
G1	108.26 \pm 19.84 ^b	
G2	88.81 \pm 19.00 ^c	
G3	68.30 \pm 14.34 ^d	

Description: Different notations indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) by Duncan's post-hoc test.

Area of Langerhans Island

From the measurement of Langerhans islet area, it was found that group N had the largest Langerhans islet area when compared to treatment groups G1, G2 and G3. The area of islets of Langerhans decreased significantly in all treatment groups (G1, G2, and G3) and the smallest islets of Langerhans were found in group G3. The area of islets of Langerhans in group G2 was not significantly different from group G1. The higher the dose of sucrose given, the smaller the diameter of the islets of Langerhans ($p < 0.05$) can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Mean Area of Langerhans Island

Groups	Mean (μm) \pm SD	p
N	14486.92 \pm 5844.07 ^a	0,00
G1	10851.49 \pm 4385.49 ^b	
G2	9001.98 \pm 4258.24 ^b	
G3	6300.83 \pm 1950.02 ^c	

Description: Different notations indicate significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$) by Duncan's post-hoc test.

Discussion

Characteristics of Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)

Adult zebrafish readily absorb molecules from water, due to their ability to regulate internal water and total solute concentrations. They operate hyperosmotically, an osmoregulatory strategy that involves continuous water uptake as a result of a higher internal salt concentration compared to the freshwater environment. The constant influx of water results in the uptake of molecules from their environment [10]. In zebrafish, glucose uptake occurs via glucose transporter, called GLUTs, which are expressed in the gills (GLUTs 1-3, 6, 8, and 10-13) and gut (GLUTs 5 and 9) [11].

Glucose metabolism in adult zebrafish and its development in zebrafish embryos is very similar to glucose metabolism in humans and other mammals. Under physiological conditions, zebrafish blood glucose levels are around 60 mg/dL (3.3 mmol/L) [12]. In addition, zebrafish also share 70% homology with mammals and 84% similarity with mammalian disease genes. Gene similarity has led to the use of zebrafish as a model to study mammalian gene function and disorders, such as metabolic syndrome. The zebrafish pancreas is also similar in structure to mammals, with two parts: endocrine and exocrine. The zebrafish endocrine cells were found to have three types of cells, α , β , and δ , which release insulin, glucagon, and somatostatin, respectively. Exocrine glands contain three types of cells, ductal cells, acinar cells, and centroacinar cells. This discovery initiated the use of zebrafish as a model to study various metabolic disorders associated with glucose metabolism [13].

Sucrose is a disaccharide consisting of fructose and glucose [14]. Sucrose or sugar is chemically included in the carbohydrate group, with the formula $C_{12}H_{22}O_{11}$. The formula consists of one molecule of glucose ($C_6H_{12}O_6$) bonded to one molecule of fructose ($C_6H_{12}O_6$) [15]. Chemicals such as sucrose have been shown to increase blood sugar levels in laboratory animals such as rats and zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). Excessive glucose consumption causes pancreatic beta cells to work less efficiently in producing the hormone insulin in response to elevated blood glucose levels. Studies have shown that sucrose administration can cause a rapid and significant increase in blood glucose levels in zebrafish. The results of a study conducted by Ullah et al found that after oral sucrose administration at a dose of 1250 mg/kgBB for 30 minutes, blood glucose levels in zebrafish increased to 13.58 mmol/L, which was significantly higher than the normal control group [16].

The average lifespan of zebrafish is about 36 to 42 months, with a maximum lifespan of up to 66 months. This means that at 12-18 months of age, a zebrafish is roughly equivalent to a human in their early twenties. To find the age correspondence for the 28-day lifespan of a zebrafish, it is necessary to convert it into months. There are approximately 30 days in a month so 28 days is equivalent to 0.93 months, which is equivalent to 0.077 years or 7.7 years of human age. Therefore, an induction of 28 days is approximately equivalent to an induction of 7.75 years in humans or so-called chronic induction [17][18].

Blood Glucose Levels

Normal blood glucose levels of adult zebrafish are around 50-75 mg/dL [19]. The results showed that an increase in sucrose concentration in aquarium water was directly proportional to the increase in blood sugar levels in zebrafish. The fish group exposed to 4% sucrose had the highest blood sugar level, which was 35% higher than the group exposed to 1% and 2% sucrose, as well as the control group. This is consistent with previous research conducted by Ranjan and Sharma in 2018 which said that immersion in different sucrose solutions below 4% tested triggered an increase in blood glucose levels up to day 14 of treatment compared to control animals [20].

The results showed a difference in blood glucose levels between G1, G2, G3 and N ($p < 0.05$). 1% sucrose induction was not different from 2% induction blood glucose levels, but significantly lower with 4%.

This increase in blood sugar levels can be explained by the mechanism of sugar metabolism, which is similar to other vertebrates. Sucrose is broken down into glucose and fructose which are then absorbed into the bloodstream, causing an increase in blood sugar levels. At higher concentrations, this effect becomes more significant, suggesting that zebrafish may have limitations in regulating blood sugar levels when exposed to high sucrose concentrations. As freshwater teleosts, zebrafish control their internal water and salt concentrations by performing hyperosmotic osmoregulation, which involves a constant influx of water, resulting in the absorption of other molecules in their environment.⁹ Carbohydrates are broken down into simple sugars, such as glucose and fructose, through enzymatic digestion in the zebrafish small intestine. This process is facilitated by enzymes such as sucrase and

maltase. The absorbed glucose and fructose are then transported across the intestinal epithelial cells. Glucose is absorbed via sodium-glucose cotransporter 1 (SGLT1) and GLUT-2. In zebrafish GLUT-2 is the major glucose transporter responsible for glucose absorption in various tissues [21].

Langerhans Island Damage

Histological analysis showed damage to the pancreatic organs of zebrafish exposed to sucrose, with the level of damage increasing with increasing sucrose concentration. The smallest percentage of damage to the islets of Langerhans pancreas was the control group with normal conditions at 3.8%, then the 1% group with mild damage which amounted to 33.8%, and the 2% group with moderate damage which amounted to 62.65%, while for the 4% group obtained severe damage with a percentage of 81.8%. The results of statistical analysis concluded that the normal control was different from the induction treatment of 1%, 2% and 4% ($P < 0.05$). Between treatments, significant differences were found, the higher the dose, the greater the percentage of damage to the islets of Langerhans.

This pancreatic damage is caused by prolonged elevated blood sugar levels, which can lead to oxidative stress and inflammation. In addition, high blood sugar levels can trigger a more intense inflammatory response, worsening the condition of the pancreas and disrupting its normal function. This statement is supported by the results of a study that said that high concentrations of sucrose can cause pancreatic inflammation and islet injury, leading to changes in pancreatic tissue morphology [22]. Another study also proved that sucrose-fed rats showed hyalinization with focal inflammatory infiltrates in pancreatic tissue, accompanied by increased macrophage infiltration and chemokine expression [23]. Another study documented that sucrose consumption caused pancreatic fibrosis and inflammation in rats, which was associated with impaired insulin secretion and hyperglycemia [24]. These findings suggest that sucrose may contribute to pancreatic damage and insulin resistance, which are key features of metabolic disorders such as type 2 diabetes.

The results of measuring the diameter of the islets of Langerhans obtained differences in the average diameter of the islets of Langerhans in each group. If sorted from the largest, the largest mean diameter result is the control group with a mean diameter of 139.11 μm , followed by G1 which is 108.26 μm , and G2 with a mean diameter of 88.81 μm , while the smallest mean diameter is G3 with 68.30 μm . Statistical analysis showed significant differences between groups of animals on the mean diameter of the islets of Langerhans ($p < 0.05$).

The results of measuring the area of the islets of Langerhans in the treatment group obtained N with a mean area of 14486.92 μm^2 , G1 by 10851.49 μm^2 , G2 by 9001.98 μm^2 , and G3 by 6300.83 μm^2 ($p < 0.05$). Between treatments, there was a significant difference between the 1% and 4% induction treatments ($p < 0.05$), and there was no significant difference between the 2% and 4% groups ($p > 0.05$). The higher the dose, the smaller the diameter of the islets of Langerhans.

The smaller diameter and area of the islets of Langerhans indicate a decrease in the number of pancreatic beta cells that function in insulin production. This suggests that high sucrose exposure not only increases blood sugar levels but also results in structural damage to pancreatic tissue, which can disrupt pancreatic endocrine function [25]. According to research by Damayanti et al. (2019) with a high fat and high fructose diet can cause damage to pancreatic beta cells and induce insulin resistance [26].

Conclusions

Based on the research results, the following conclusions were obtained:

1. Sucrose induction 4% causes the highest increase in glucose levels of 188.67 mg/dL.
2. Sucrose induction 4% causes pancreatic damage characterized by a decrease in the area and diameter of the islets of Langerhans by 81.8% compared to normal.

Suggestion

Based on this study, the suggestion for future research is to conduct further studies to evaluate the effect of sucrose induction on the number of pancreatic beta cells and pancreatic alpha cells using immunohistochemistry.

References

- [1] Budianto, R. E., Linawati, N. M., Arijana, I. G. K. N., Wahyuniari, I. A. I., & Wiryawan, I. G. N. S. (2022). Potensi Senyawa Fitokimia pada Tumbuhan dalam Menurunkan Kadar Glukosa Darah pada Diabetes Melitus. *Jurnal Sains Dan Kesehatan*, 4(5), 548–556. <https://doi.org/10.25026/jsk.v4i5.1259>

- [2] Cahyaningrum, N. (2023). Hubungan Pola Makan 3J (Jumlah, Jenis, Jadwal) Dan Perilaku Sedentari Dengan Pengendalian Gula Darah Pasien Dm Tipe 2. *Nutrition Research and Development Journal*, 03(1), 12–23.
- [3] Sami, W., Ansari, T., Butt, N. S., Rashid, M., & Hamid, A. (2017). Effect Of Diet Counseling on Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Review. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 11(2), 65–71. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5426415/pdf/IJHS-11-65.pdf>
- [4] Malik, V. S., Popkin, B. M., Bray, G. A., Després, J. P., Willett, W. C., & Hu, F. B. (2010). Sugar-sweetened beverages and risk of metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes: A meta-analysis. *Diabetes Care*, 33(11), 2477–2483. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc10-1079>
- [5] Usnaini, L., Winangun, Musyarrifah, & Wanadiatri, H. (2020). Hubungan Kepatuhan Konsumsi Obat Antidiabetik Terhadap Kadar HBA1C Pada Pasien di Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah Provinsi Nusa Tenggara Barat Tahun 2019. *Jurnal Kedokteran*, 5(2), 69–79.
- [6] Tiurma, R. J., & Syahrizal. (2021). Obesitas Sentral dengan Kejadian Hiperglikemia pada Pegawai Satuan Kerja Perangkat Daerah. *Higeia Journal of Public Health Research and Development*, 5(3), 354–364.
- [7] Mirontoneng, G. S., Kairupan, C. F., Durry, M. F., Studi, P., Dokter, P., Kedokteran, F., Sam, U., Manado, R., Patologi, B., Fakultas, A., Universitas, K., & Manado, S. R. (2019). Gambaran Mikroskopik Endokrin Pankreas pada Tikus Wistar yang Diberikan Sukrosa Dosis Bertingkat. *Jurnal E-Biomedik*, 7(2), 108–112.
- [8] Yuniastuti, A., Susanti, R., & Iswari, R. S. (2018). Efek Infusa Umbi Garut (*Marantha arundinaceae* L) Terhadap Kadar Glukosa dan Insulin Plasma Tikus yang Diinduksi Streptozotocyn. *Jurnal Mipa*, 41(1), 34–39.
- [9] Shehwana, H., & Konu, O. (2019). Comparative Transcriptomics Between Zebrafish and Mammals: A Roadmap for Discovery of Conserved and Unique Signaling Pathways in Physiology and Disease. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*, 7(5), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2019.00005>
- [10] Ranjan, S., & Sharma, P. K. (2018). *Development of High Sugar Induced Hyperglycemia or Type 2 Diabetes in Zebrafish (Danio rerio) Model*. 8(3), 6–12. <https://doi.org/10.37591/rrjohp.v8i3.375>
- [11] Capiotti, K. M., Antonioli, R., Kist, L. W., Bogo, M. R., Bonan, C. D., & Da Silva, R. S. (2014). Persistent impaired glucose metabolism in a zebrafish hyperglycemia model. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part - B: Biochemistry and Molecular Biology*, 171(1), 58–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbpb.2014.03.005>
- [12] Heckler, K., & Kroll, J. (2017). Zebrafish as a model for the study of microvascular complications of diabetes and their mechanisms. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 18(9), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms18092002>
- [13] Benchoula, K., Khatib, A., Quzwain, F. M. C., Che Mohamad, C. A., Wan Sulaiman, W. M. A., Wahab, R. A., Ahmed, Q. U., Ghaffar, M. A., Saiman, M. Z., Alajmi, M. F., & El-Seedi, H. (2019). Optimization of hyperglycemic induction in zebrafish and evaluation of its blood glucose level and metabolite fingerprint treated with psychotria malayana Jack Leaf extract. *Molecules*, 24(8), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules24081506>
- [14] Lara-Cruz, G. A., & Jaramillo-Botero, A. (2022). Molecular Level Sucrose Quantification: A Critical Review. *Sensors*, 22(23), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22239511>
- [15] Anwar, D. (2019). Perbandingan Hidrolisis Gula Aren Dan Gula Pasir Dengan Katalis Matriks Polistirena Terikat Silang (Crosslink). *Jurnal Ilmiah Kohesi*, 3(3), 15–20.
- [16] Ullah, S., Huyop, F., Huda, N., Ab Wahab, R., Hamid, A. A. A., Mohamad, M. A. N., Ahmad, H. F., Shariff, A. H. M., & Nasir, M. H. M. (2024). Green honey of Banggi Island: A preliminary anti-diabetic study on zebrafish model. *Heliyon*, 10(4), e26469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e26469>
- [17] Kijima, Y., Wantong, W., Igarashi, Y., Yoshitake, K., Asakawa, S., Suzuki, Y., Watabe, S., & Kinoshita, S. (2022). Age-Associated Different Transcriptome Profiling in Zebrafish and Rats: an Insight into the Diversity of Vertebrate Aging. In *Marine Biotechnology* (Vol. 24, Issue 5).
- [18] Keller, E. T., & Murtha, J. M. (2004). The use of mature zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) as a model for human aging and disease. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology - C Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 138(3), 335–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2004.04.001>
- [19] Eti Rohaeti, Dea Nurafifah, & Irmanida Batubara. (2022). Antidiabetic Activity of Manonjaya Snakefruit Skin Extract with Zebra Fish (*Danio rerio*) as Animal Model. *Jurnal Jamu Indonesia*, 7(3), 102–110. <https://doi.org/10.29244/jji.v7i3.201>

- [20] Ranjan, S., & Sharma, P. K. (2020). Study of learning and memory in type 2 diabetic model of zebrafish (*Danio rerio*). *Endocrine and Metabolic Science*, 1(3–4), 100058.
- [21] Moss, J. B., Koustubhan, P., Greenman, M., Parsons, M. J., Walter, I., & Moss, L. G. (2009). Regeneration of the pancreas in adult zebrafish. *Diabetes*, 58(8), 1844–1851.
- [22] Xi, L., Zhai, G., Liu, Y., Gong, Y., Lu, Q., Zhang, Z., Liu, H., Jin, J., Zhu, X., Yin, Z., Xie, S., & Han, D. (2023). Attenuated glucose uptake promotes catabolic metabolism through activated AMPK signaling and impaired insulin signaling in zebrafish. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 10.
- [23] Roncal-Jimenez, C. A., Lanaspa, M. A., Rivard, C. J., Nakagawa, T., Sanchez-Lozada, L. G., Jalal, D., Andres-Hernando, A., Tanabe, K., Madero, M., Li, N., Cicerchi, C., McFann, K., Sautin, Y. Y., & Johnson, R. J. (2011). Sucrose induces fatty liver and pancreatic inflammation in male breeder rats independent of excess energy intake. *Metabolism: Clinical and Experimental*, 60(9), 1259–1270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.metabol.2011.01.008>
- [24] Cruz, E. M. S., Morais, J. M. B. De, Rosa, C. V. D. Da, Simoes, M. D. S., Comar, J. F., Chuffa, L. G. D. A., & Seiva, F. R. F. (2020). Long-term sucrose solution consumption causes metabolic alterations and affects hepatic oxidative stress in Wistar rats. *Biology Open*, 9(3), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1242/bio.047282>
- [25] Wijayanti, N. P. P., Hendriati, L., Hamid, I. S., Widodo, T., & Kuncorojakti, S. (2023). Efektivitas Patch Transdermal Ekstrak Etanol Daun Insulin (*Smallanthus sonchifolius*) Terhadap Kadar Glukosa Darah dan Histopatologi Pankreas Tikus Putih. *JPSCR: Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Clinical Research*, 8(2), 152. <https://doi.org/10.20961/jpscr.v8i2.59508>
- [26] Damayanti, D. S., Kusuma, H. M. S. C., & Soeatmadji, D. W. (2019). Soursop (*Annona muricata*) Leaf Water Extract (SLWE) Prevent Pancreatic B-Cell Damage in Male Wistar Rats Induced By High Fat and High Fructose (HFHF) Diet. *International Journal of Diabetes & Metabolic Disorders*, 4(6), 4-11.